

Data set 1: Geographic, characteristic and seasonally of distinct freshwater bodies (n=18)

* For Dalton site: sample collected on Nov. 2014 and on Mar, May, Nov. 2015

Data set 2: Longitudinal - time series of aquaculture reservoir (n=23)

DARU aquaculture facility (Dor)-Spring water

Samples were taken ~monthly over 2 years using GFF filter)

Data set 3: Algal bloom - Lake Kinneret -Water column (Mar-Apr 2015, n=16)

(i) Depth 0m (Surface, n=4)

(ii) Depth 1m (n=4)

(iii) Depth 5m (n=4)

(iv) Integrated sample of all depth (20μm filter size, n=4))

←0.22 and 5μm filters